

THE ROLE AND SIGNIFICANCE OF LISTENING LESSONS IN LEARNING THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE IN SENIOR CLASSES OF GENERAL SECONDARY SCHOOLS

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Annotation: In this article, the study of the hearing problems of senior secondary school students and the factors that lead to students' hearing difficulties are described. The article also provides an analysis of the main problems in students' listening skills and some strategies and methods to help improve their listening skills.

Key words: foreign languages, structural methods, modern textbooks and training manuals.

Introduction.

Listening, or listening comprehension, is the first and most important skill that language learners need to learn when learning a new language. This is a receptive skill, meaning that new language learners learn new words from what they hear or listen to. The ability to receive affects the ability to produce. If only they knew how to listen; as a result, they understand effective skills, i.e. speaking and writing, and even have good speech. To be a good listener, students need to think actively while listening. Listening is involved in many language learning processes, both in and out of the language classroom. Improving listening skills is the basis for developing other language skills.

For many years, listening comprehension skills were not a priority in language teaching. Educational methods emphasized productive skills, and it became clear that the relationship between receptive and productive skills was not well understood. Until recently, the nature of second language listening comprehension has been neglected by applied linguists, and it has often been assumed that listening skills can be acquired through exposure but not actually learned. This position was replaced by an active interest in the role of listening comprehension in second language acquisition, and the development of strong theories about the nature of language comprehension. Sometimes people think of listening as a passive skill. In fact, the ability to listen requires the active participation of the listener. The listener must actively incorporate knowledge from linguistic and non-linguistic sources to reconstruct the message the speaker is trying to convey. Listening is an active process in which the receiver takes responsibility. It also requires a response from the listener. Actions, facial expressions and applause can be the answer. Listening is very important in learning English. Anyone who wants to learn English well should be able to master listening comprehension as one of the English language skills. By learning listening skills, people can learn English faster than before. Listening also plays an important role in conversation because people can respond after listening to the speaker. Since listening is important for understanding the spoken message, listening skills cannot be neglected in teaching English. Developing teaching and learning strategies for teachers to help students develop listening skills. Listening practice is probably the most reliable way to lead to real communication, because the speaking skills of

students can be considered weak, because they do not know how to express their feelings and thoughts during listening, conversation, communication. In fact, listening to English is very useful for all students to deepen or improve their language skills.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY.

From the point of view of linguistics, the following factors can interfere with the understanding of a foreign language: the speed of speech, the complexity of language structures and vocabulary, phonological features (for example, dialect or foreign accent, different speakers), the absence of visual effects, background noise and occasional difficulty concentrating or hearing. From the point of view of the subject (content), the basic knowledge of the subject is very important. If the listener is not familiar with the topic, this can make the comprehension process difficult - the cognitive load that the material presents can be too high. Listening material in a language class usually challenges students' language knowledge and skills and rarely affects cognitive skills, while material in a content class is concerned with thought processes and specific content. requires the exception of related terms. During a language lesson, students usually listen to recorded real-life situations that show, for example, how a foreign language is used. an excerpt from a story, dialogue, debate, film or radio show. The listening material in the subject lesson focuses on the academic context, the focus is on information, and the speaker is often of secondary importance. In addition, the main source of listening is the teacher himself. Another common resource is explainer videos that show aspects of a topic that can't be shown otherwise. During the language learning process, language learners face several challenges; most of them can occur during the listening comprehension process. Scientists have identified the following problems:

Quality of recorded materials. In some classes, teachers use recorded materials that are not of high quality. The quality of the sound system can affect students' listening comprehension;

Cultural differences. Learners need to be familiar with cultural language skills that significantly affect comprehension. If the listening task involves material from a completely different culture, students may experience significant comprehension problems. Teachers should provide basic knowledge of pre-listening activities;

Accent. Too much accented speech can cause a significant decrease in intelligibility. According to Goh (1999), 66% of students rated speaker's accent as one of the most important factors affecting listener comprehension. Unfamiliar accents, both native and non-native, can cause serious listening comprehension problems, and familiarizing yourself with the accent can help students with listening comprehension. Listeners have serious listening difficulties when they hear an unfamiliar accent such as Indian English for the first time after only learning American English.

Unfamiliar vocabulary. If there are a lot of specific words in the specific listening texts, it will be easier for the students to approach them. If students know the meaning of the words, it can stimulate their interest and motivation and have a positive effect on students' listening skills.

Length and speed of listening. It can be important for students to listen to long passages and remember all the information. This can be difficult for young learners and students. Listening and listening tasks for more than three minutes are now acceptable for language learners. Short listening passages facilitate students' listening comprehension and reduce their fatigue.

Active listening is an example of understanding. Today, using active listening is worth becoming a better communicator, increasing productivity and improving relationships. Perhaps the most important skill children learn is the ability to listen carefully and understand what they hear. The level of students' listening skills can affect their academic performance as well as the classroom environment. By using a variety of creative activities, teachers can help students develop strong listening skills that will help them throughout their academic careers. By raising students' awareness of listening as an active skill and teaching specific listening strategies, teachers can help their students develop the skills and confidence to handle communication situations they may encounter outside of the classroom. In this way, they create the basis for communicative competence in the new language. Using the general knowledge of developing language skills, we can list some recommendations for developing listening skills:

Listening skills are developed through face-to-face communication. By communicating in English, students have the opportunity to introduce a new language and test their listening skills. Face-to-face communication develops the ability to listen for meaning.

Listening is developed by focusing on meaning and trying to learn new and important content in the target language. By focusing on the meaning and real reasons for listening in English, students can develop their linguistic and non-linguistic comprehension skills.

Listening skills are developed by working on comprehension activities. By focusing on specific listening objectives, students can assess their own efforts and abilities. With well-defined comprehension activities, students have the opportunity to assess and revise what they have achieved.

Listening is developed by paying attention to accuracy and analyzing form. By learning to correctly perceive sounds and words, our students can achieve sustainable development if they carry out meaningfully oriented activities. By learning to hear sounds and words more clearly, students are confident they understand the meaning.

Listening as understanding is a traditional way of thinking about the nature of listening. In fact, in many methodical manuals, listening and hearing are synonymous. This view of listening is based on the assumption that the primary function of listening in second language learning is to facilitate comprehension of spoken language. Some scholars offer the following views: the first principle of improving listening is to choose appropriate resources for students at different levels and according to their different needs. There is a wide variety of listening material we can use: videotapes, films, BBC news, songs, recorded tapes and even 'live' material. In addition, it is easy for teachers to prepare well for the audition before coming to class. But teachers should listen to the materials themselves before bringing them into the classroom, because teachers need to know where students might be having trouble and when to pause and explain. In addition, Underwood says that without seeing the speaker while listening, learners must focus on what they hear instead of relying on paralinguistic cues to infer the meaning of what is being said. The second principle of improving listening skills is how to plan appropriate tasks, exercises or activities for students. When designing listening exercises, we need to consider the following factors. First, keep in mind what real-life situation we are preparing for students, and the specific challenges they may face and need practice to overcome, and one of the goals of teachers in teaching listening is to teach students to listen with goals and expectations. should be taught. By setting a listening goal, students listen more attentively and thus listen more successfully because they can listen

selectively without having to memorize every detail of what they hear. Second, we need to plan activities or activities according to the characteristics of the classroom, such as class size, number of students, or availability of equipment. Third, and most importantly, try to increase students' interest and motivate them. Student motivation is a critical factor in successful learning, so if a student can successfully complete simple tasks, he or she will have more confidence to practice other skills. Conversely, students who are given tasks that are difficult to understand are less motivated because they are unable to complete the tasks. Failure to do so may even lead to the formation of one of the passive and unsuccessful listening habits, where listeners equate "*listening*" with sitting back and swallowing a largely meaningless sequence of sounds. Choosing topics should not be too difficult or too easy. If teachers provide adequate support to students prior to listening, students can selectively attend to relevant parts, thereby reducing the amount of information processing and memorization. Pre-listening support allows students to achieve higher levels of achievement and thus build confidence.

Listening exercises are designed to help students develop the skills to extract information from spoken speech. Teachers can use listening exercises to give students an opportunity to practice their ability to predict, compare and interpret what they have learned from listening to their language. Good listening activities can help students move through the listening text based on their pre-listening expectations, but they should be fun and something most students can do, as failure to complete the task can lead to demotivation.

"Everything in writing begins with language. Language begins with listening" (*Jianette Winterson*). The art of listening is nothing but recognizing and understanding what others are saying. It revolves around three factors:

- *Understanding the pronunciation and accent of the speaker;*
- *Learning syntax and vocabulary;*
- *Understanding the speaker's intent.*

Because listening is a complex and complex skill, students must develop it through practice. Listening is key in learning a foreign language. It serves as a key factor for learning and developing other language skills. According to scientists, the following exercises are specially designed to improve listening skills:

1. The main meaning of listening - as the name suggests, the main mechanism of this activity is that the information necessary to perform the task (for example, attending a meeting) is distributed among 3-4 groups in the class. Each group listens to the recorded material and writes the available information on a sheet. The groups then come together to pool their information.

2. Vague conversations - students listen to a short conversation (or a fragment of a long conversation) that gives very little information about what the speakers are talking about. Readers must decide for themselves who is speaking, where they are, what they are talking about, and perhaps what happens next. So this type of listening naturally leads to discussion (and writing, if you like).

3. Decision-making - students are presented with some information, for example, about the city (directions, facilities, etc.) in the form of a conversation or conversation, based on which they should plan a visit. Planning involves discussion and note taking. Decision-making activities may also involve, for example, choosing between locations, events, activities for which basic information is available in recorded form.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, listening is a complex skill that must be developed through practice. Teachers should provide opportunities for their students to reflect on their listening processes and practices. The role of the teacher is very important, because the teacher not only guides the students in the listening process, but also encourages them and allows them to control their knowledge. Most English programs do not focus on listening comprehension. Listening is a difficult process. Listening comprehension strategies should be used simultaneously. When we listen to a text, we need to understand, retain information in memory, combine it with the next, and understand what we heard through previous knowledge and subsequent information.

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